

Invited Review

Obesity and NRF2-mediated cytoprotection: Where is the missing link?

Liliya V. Vasileva^a, Martina S. Savova^{a,b}, Kristiana M. Amirova^{a,b}, Albena T. Dinkova-Kostova^{c,d}, Milen I. Georgiev^{a,b,*}

^a Department of Plant Cell Biotechnology, Center of Plant Systems Biology and Biotechnology, 4000 Plovdiv, Bulgaria

^b Laboratory of Metabolomics, The Stephan Angeloff Institute of Microbiology, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 139 Ruski Blvd., 4000 Plovdiv, Bulgaria

^c Jacqui Wood Cancer Centre, Division of Cellular Medicine, School of Medicine, University of Dundee, Dundee, DD1 9SY, Scotland, UK

^d Department of Pharmacology and Molecular Sciences and Department of Medicine, Johns Hopkins University School of Medicine, Baltimore, MD 21205, USA

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ABSTRACT

The expanding dimensions of the global health crisis of overweight population has defined the term “globesity”. Among the most common pathological conditions connected with excessive adiposity are hyperglycemia, insulin resistance, dyslipidemia and hypertension which result in chronic non-communicable diseases (NCD) such as metabolic syndrome (MetS), type 2 diabetes (T2D), and nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH). The contribution of inflammatory-immune reactions in obesity and its related co-morbidities is unequivocal. Increased levels of free fatty acids (FFA), reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) overloads the homeostatic system resulting in pro-inflammatory adipokines secretion, immune-activation and chronic inflammation in obesity. The cellular mechanisms of defense against oxidative stress are orchestrated by the transcription factor nuclear factor erythroid 2 p45-related factor 2 (NRF2). Excessive oxidative stress in the cell activates NRF2 which upregulates genes encoding major cytoprotective enzymes such as NAD(P)H:quinone oxidoreductase 1 (NQO1), heme oxygenase 1 (HO1), and glutathione S-transferases (GST). The present review aims to clarify the interconnections between chronic inflammation, oxidative overload and NRF2-mediated cytoprotection as potential therapeutic approach in obesity.

1. Introduction

The expanding dimensions of the global health crisis of overweight

population is what has defined the term “globesity” in the recent years. In the period between 1975 and 2016 along with the intensive economic and technological developments, the rates of obesity have nearly

Abbreviations: Acc, acetyl-CoA carboxylase; AhR, aryl hydrocarbon receptor; Akt, protein kinase B; AMPK, AMP-activated protein kinase; ARE, antioxidant response elements; ATM, adipose tissue macrophages; BAT, brown adipose tissue; BH4, tetrahydrobiopterin; BTB, Broad complex Tramtrack and Bric-a-Brac; BW, body weight; C/EBPs, CAAT/enhancer-binding proteins; CAT, catalase; CBP, cAMP response element-binding protein (CREB)-binding protein; CD, cluster of differentiation; CDDO, 2-cyano-3,12-dioxoolean-1,9-dien-28-oic acid; CHD, chromo-ATPase/helicase DNA-binding protein; CNcZIP, Cap'n'Collar basic leucine zipper; COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; CUL3, cullin 3; CYP1B1, cytochrome P450 1B1; DIO, diet-induced obesity; ERK, extracellular signal-regulated kinase; FABP4, fatty acid binding protein 4; FAS, fatty acid synthase; FFA, free fatty acids; FGF21, fibroblast growth factor 21; GCH1, GTP cyclohydrolase 1; GLUT4, glucose transporter type 4; GPX, glutathione peroxidase; GSH, glutathione; GSK, glycogen synthase kinase; GST, glutathione S-transferases; HCD, high carbohydrates diet; HFD, high fat diet; HFFD, high fat and fructose diet; HO-1, heme oxygenase 1; IGF1, insulin growth factor 1; IL, interleukin; IR, insulin resistance; IVR, intervening region domain; JNK, c-Jun N-terminal kinase; KD, knockdown; KEAP1, Kelch-like ECH-associated protein 1; KO, knockout; MAPK, mitogen-activated protein kinase; MCP, monocyte chemoattractant protein; MetS, metabolic syndrome; mTOR, mechanistic target of Rapamycin; NASH, nonalcoholic steatohepatitis; NFE2L2, transcription factor nuclear factor erythroid 2 p45-related factor 2 gene; nNOS, neuronal nitric oxide synthase; NCD, non-communicable diseases; Neh, NRF2-ECH homology; NF-κB, nuclear factor-kappa B; Nox, NADPH oxidase gene; NQO-1, NAD(P)H:quinone oxidoreductase 1; NRF2, transcription factor nuclear factor erythroid 2 p45-related factor 2; p62, ubiquitin-binding protein 62; PGC1α, PPAR gamma receptor – co-activator 1 alpha; PPAR, peroxisome proliferator receptor; RAC, receptor-associated co-activator; RNS, reactive nitrogen species; ROS, reactive oxygen species; RXRα, retinoid X receptor alpha; sMaf, small musculoaponeurotic fibrosarcoma oncogene homologue; SGBS, Simpson-Golabi-Behmel syndrome; SOD, superoxide dismutase; SQSTM1, sequestosome 1; SREBP-1, sterol regulatory element binding protein 1; T2D, type 2 diabetes; TBE-31, tricyclic bis(cyanoenone) compound; TG, triglycerides; TGF-β, transforming growth factor beta; TNF-α, tumor necrosis factor alpha; TRAIL, TNF-related apoptosis inducing ligand; WAT, white adipose tissue; WT, wild type; β-TrCP, beta transducin repeat-containing protein

* Corresponding author at: Laboratory of Metabolomics, The Stephan Angeloff Institute of Microbiology, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 139 Ruski Blvd., 4000 Plovdiv, Bulgaria.

E-mail address: milengeorgiev@gbg.bg (M.I. Georgiev).

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tripled. Globally, the countries where more than 20 % of the adult population is not only overweight but obese exceed those where starvation is a substantial problem [1]. Recent analysis by the World Health Organization from 2017 reports that about two billion of people on the planet are overweight and about one third of them are obese. Furthermore, these numbers are expected to grow in the next decades along with the rate of obesity-related health complications. Among the most common pathological conditions connected with excessive adiposity are hyperglycemia, insulin resistance, dyslipidemia and hypertension which result in chronic non-communicable diseases (NCD) such as metabolic syndrome (MetS), type 2 diabetes (T2D), nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), etc [2].

The pathogenesis of obesity is no longer described as a simple imbalance between energy storage and use, and the adipose tissue is defined as an important endocrine organ. The key role of the adipokines leptin, adiponectin and resistin in lipogenesis, lipolysis and mediating the communication with other tissues as well as sending satiety/hunger signals to the brain has been established [2]. The energy balance also depends on age. In their longitudinal clinical study Arner et al. [3] followed up the lipid turnover in control and morbidly obese adults over a period of up to 16 years based on the lipid age. The results of this study suggest that the balance between lipid accumulation and removal in humans changes with age in favor of decrease in the lipolysis rate [3]. These novel findings point towards shifting the obesity interventions from attempting to increase lipid removal rates to searching for potential mechanisms to decrease adipogenesis. The past two decades of targeted research efforts in obesity and metabolic disorders defined the mechanisms involved as multifactorial and highly complex; these have been recently reviewed [2].

The contribution of inflammatory-immune reactions in obesity and its related co-morbidities is unequivocal [4]. The pathogenesis of obesity features increase in the circulating levels of free fatty acids (FFA), reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS). The limited ability of the homeostatic system to manage these challenges leads to leptin and insulin signaling dysregulations in adipose, muscular and hepatic tissues. Consequently, in adipose tissue the elevated FFA and ROS levels induce pro-inflammatory adipokines secretion, immune-activation and result in chronic inflammation [5]. Macrophages resident in the adipose tissue (ATM) predominantly shift their phenotype from the protective class 2 (ATM2) to the pro-inflammatory class 1 (ATM1) and further exacerbate the inflammatory environment in fat tissue [2,6].

The cellular mechanisms of defense against oxidative and inflammatory stress are orchestrated by the transcription factor nuclear factor erythroid2 p45-related factor 2 (NRF2, encoded by *NFE2L2* gene). Under stress conditions, NRF2 is activated which results in the upregulation of genes encoding major protective enzymes such as NAD(P)H:quinone oxidoreductase 1 (NQO1), heme oxygenase 1 (HO1), glutathione S-transferases (GST), aldo-ketoreductases, γ -glutamylcysteine ligase, thioredoxin, and thioredoxin reductase [7,8]. In addition, NRF2 activation has potent anti-inflammatory effects, and plays a critical role in the resolution of inflammation [9–11]. The utility of pharmacological NRF2 activation as a therapeutic approach was demonstrated by the approval of dimethyl fumarate under the brand name Tecfidera for the management of relapsing-remitting multiple sclerosis in 2014. The role of NRF2 in NCD and the pharmacological modulators targeting the transcription factor that are currently at various stages of drug development, have been extensively reviewed by Cuadrado et al. [12]. The potential implementation of NRF2 as a target for T2D therapy has also been reviewed by Matzinger et al. [3] and earlier by Uruno et al. [14]. However, with respect to obesity, the reported effects of its modulation are controversial. Therefore, the present review aims to clarify the interconnections between chronic inflammation, oxidative overload and NRF2-mediated cytoprotection as a potential therapeutic approach in obesity.

2. The role of oxidative stress in obesity

Commitment for adipogenesis could be induced in stem cells by extracellular signals, such as insulin growth factor 1 (IGF1), interleukin (IL) 17, transforming growth factor β (TGF- β) or intracellular factors, including increased levels of ROS, decreased levels of reduced glutathione (GSH), protein kinase B (Akt), among others [15]. The transcriptional cascade of adipogenesis orchestrated by the CAAT/enhancer-binding proteins (C/EBPs) – C/EBP β and C/EBP δ at the early stages, and C/EBP α which interacts with peroxisome proliferator receptor γ (PPAR γ) and sterol regulatory element binding protein 1 (SREBP-1), at the later stages of differentiation. These mechanisms ensure the energy storing function of the adipocytes at homeostatic conditions. Nutritional overload that persists for prolonged periods, at certain point can exceed the physiological capacity of the adipose tissue and lead to systemic glucotoxicity, lipotoxicity and increased pro-inflammatory adipokine productions as hallmarks for obesity [4]. Impairment of the balance of the production of adipokines is associated with increased oxidative responses. The inflammatory secretion profile of adipocytes include increased leptin, tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α), IL-1 β , IL-6 and IL-8, monocyte chemoattractant protein 1 (MCP-1) and TNF-related apoptosis inducing ligand (TRAIL) among others [16]. Hill et al. [17] concluded that macrophage infiltration in adipose tissue is exacerbated by elevation in the levels of nuclear factor-kappa B (NF- κ B) which leads to increased life-span of activated pro-inflammatory macrophages and formation of the vicious cycle of inflammation. Additionally, the obese adipocytes overloaded with triglycerides (TGs) are activating the resident ATMs to secrete TNF- α and in turn TNF- α is inducing FFA release from the hypertrophic fat cells resulting in oxidative milieu [18].

Excess of substrates for the intermediary metabolic pathways resulting from the elevated circulating glucose and lipids in obesity could be overwhelming for the mitochondria and leads to overproduction of ROS. While ROS play crucial role in cell signaling and at low levels induce differentiation, if left to accumulate their high levels are harmful to cellular proteins, lipids and DNA [19]. A large number of experimental and clinical studies have associated obesity and its complications with increased oxidative stress. Adipogenesis in human Simpson-Golabi-Behmel syndrome (SGBS) adipocytes is influenced by elevated ROS through decrease in adiponectin and extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK) activity [20]. Increase in the production of ROS in the hypertrophic adipocytes in the white adipose tissue (WAT) in leptin deficient *ob/ob* mice was found, along with upregulation of the NADPH oxidase (*Nox*) genes *Nox1* and *Nox2* [21]. A clinical study evaluating oxidative stress markers in patients with MetS and obesity or T2D found in both groups decreased glutathione levels, catalase (CAT), superoxide dismutase (SOD) activities and increased total and mitochondrial ROS levels compared to metabolically healthy controls. Moreover, the disrupted oxidative status correlates with dyslipidemia and inflammatory markers, such as increased TNF- α and insulin resistance (IR) that are present in obese patients [22].

3. The KEAP1/NRF2/ARE signaling pathway

Preservation of the cell integrity includes mechanisms of defense against oxidative stress. The gene expression of cytoprotective proteins is mainly regulated through the Cap'n'Collar basic leucine zipper (CNC/bZIP) transcription factor NRF2 [23]. Under homeostatic conditions NRF2 is bound to the Kelch-like ECH-associated protein 1 (KEAP1) which acts as a substrate adaptor for a Cullin 3 (CUL3)-based ubiquitin ligase, presenting NRF2 for ubiquitination and proteasomal degradation [8,12]. In addition to being a repressor of NRF2, KEAP1 plays a key role as intracellular sensor for chemical inducers, including ROS and RNS, by virtue of its specific cysteine sensors [24,25].

Seven NRF2-ECH homology (Neh) domains are defined within the structure of NRF2 with each serving a specific function. The Neh2

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of KEAP1 (A) and NRF2 (B). The positions of NRF2 and KEAP1 domains are indicated with their respective amino acids numbering. In basal conditions, homodimeric KEAP1 binds *via* its Kelch domain to the ETGE and DGL motifs in the Neh2 domain of NRF2, and *via* its BTB domain to CUL3, leading to ubiquitination and proteosomal degradation of NRF2. Chemical modification of specific cysteine sensors of KEAP1 (exemplified by cys151, cys273, and cys288) inactivates KEAP1, resulting in accumulation of *de novo* synthesized NRF2 and its nuclear translocation. In the nucleus (C), NRF2 forms a heterodimer with a sMaf protein, which binds to ARE-containing genes and activates their transcription.

domain contains the DLG and ETGE motifs which are the KEAP1 binding sites. The NRF2 transactivation site is formed by the Neh4 and Neh5 domains that recruit cAMP response element-binding protein (CREB)-binding protein (CBP) and/or receptor-associated co-activator (RAC) 3. The Neh7 domain upon binding with retinoid X receptor α (RXR α) initiates suppression of the NRF2-mediated transcription. The Neh6 domain, and more specifically its DSGIS and DSAPGS motifs, function as the binding site for β -transducin repeat-containing protein (β -TrCP) which, following phosphorylation by glycogen synthase kinase 3 (GSK-3), leads to NRF2 degradation. The Neh1 domain is responsible for binding to the DNA and the small musculoaponeurotic fibrosarcoma oncogene homologue (sMaf) protein and the Neh3 domain recruits chromo-ATPase/helicase DNA-binding protein (CHD) 6 [13,19].

Electrophiles, ROS, and RNS chemically modify specific cysteine sensors of KEAP1, impairing its substrate adaptor function, and consequently leading to NRF2 stabilization and nuclear translocation. Subsequently, in the nucleus NRF2 forms a heterodimer with a sMaf protein and induces transcription of genes that contain antioxidant response element (ARE) sequences (Fig. 1). Enzymes and proteins involved in the biotransformation of xenobiotics, the maintenance of the redox balance, and the regulation of inflammation, as well as proteins regulating the hepatic lipogenesis and gluconeogenesis are encoded by ARE-containing NRF2 target genes [8,19,22]. Activation of NRF2 could also result from interaction of KEAP1 with the ubiquitin-binding protein 62 (p62) also known as sequestosome-1 (SQSTM1), which functions as a cargo protein that targets other proteins for selective autophagy [26]. Deficiency in autophagy or overproduction of p62 leads to competitive interaction with the DLG motif of NRF2 for the KEAP1 binding site and subsequently the stabilization of NRF2 [27].

The activation of NRF2 by electrophilic compounds that modify cysteine sensors in KEAP1 has been widely studied; selected examples are shown in Table 1. Whereas the organosulfur compound derived from broccoli sulforaphane is the most extensively studied and the most potent naturally occurring NRF2 inducer [28], the C-28 methyl ester of

the 2-cyano-312-dioxoolean-1,9-dien-28-oic acid (CDDO-Me) is among the most potent ones [29]. Additionally, a growing number of studies suggest novel applications for known NRF2 activators. Lefaki et al. [30] suggest that the *Glycyrrhiza*-derived triterpenoid 18 α -glycyrrhetic acid, which is a known NRF2 inducer, could be combined with mitomycin C to prevent genotoxicity. Considering that many of the known NRF2 activators are plant-derived compounds there is an intensive scientific interest in the search for potential leads from new plant sources. For example, the plant derived polyphenol bergenin has beneficial effects in diabetic nephropathy and the suggested mechanism is activation of NRF2 in KEAP1-independent manner *via* mechanistic target of Rapamycin (mTOR)/ β -TrCP pathway [31]. Withaferin A from *Withania somnifera*, which has shown preventive and therapeutic effects against multiple diseases in experimental models, activates NRF2 in a KEAP1-independent, PTEN/PI3K/AKT-dependent manner [32]. Alternative approaches to target NRF2 with non-electrophilic compounds disrupting the protein - protein interactions with KEAP1 or through KEAP1-independent mechanisms merit further exploration [8,33].

Negative modulation of NRF2 activity is relatively less explored compared to the transcription factor stimulation and mainly in the context of different types of cancer [34]. Unselective and excessive activation of NRF2 is known to contribute to the development of resistance to multiple therapies in cancer cells [35]. Considering that exploration of NRF2 inhibitors is of potential interest and not only in cancers but also in chronic NCD associated with elevated oxidative stress levels, such as obesity.

4. The modulation of NRF2 as potential approach in obesity management

The pharmacological modulation of NRF2 has been implemented in the therapy of chronic diseases such as psoriasis and multiple sclerosis represented by the dimethyl ester of fumaric acid marketed under the brand name Tecfidera. Ongoing pre-clinical and clinical investigations are exploring the potential benefits of KEAP1-dependent NRF2

Table 1
Selected examples of NRF2 activators and their mechanism of action.

Compound	Chemical structure	Source	Mechanism of action	Potential therapeutic application	Reference
Bardoxolone methyl (CDDO-Me)		Synthetic cyanoenone triterpenoid	Binds to cys151 in KEAP1 leading to NRF2 activation	Pulmonary arterial hypertension and diabetic nephropathy	[13,23,56]
Sulforaphane		<i>Brassica oleracea</i> L. and other plant species from Brassicaceae family	Binds to cys151 in KEAP1 leading to NRF2 activation	NCD	[19,57]
Curcumin		<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Modification of cysteines of KEAP1 leading to NRF2 activation	NCD	[19]
Dimethyl fumarate		Synthetic fumaric acid derivative	Binds to cys151 in KEAP1 leading to NRF2 activation	Psoriasis and multiple sclerosis	[58]
Mitoquinone		Synthetic quinone	Activates NRF2 through induction of Atg7-dependent autophagy, which leads to degradation of KEAP1	Breast cancer, nephropathies	[59,60,61]

activation in various pathologies such as T2D, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), certain types of cancer, kidney and eye diseases comprehensively reviewed elsewhere [12]. Regarding the role of NRF2 in adipogenesis and obesity-related inflammation the experimental results are controversial. This complex picture is expected when taking into consideration the large number of genes regulated by NRF2 and the diverse functions of their respective proteins within the intermediary metabolism [23]. In the next section we present a selection of experimental studies reporting results from both cell culture and animal models in an attempt to clarify the link between NRF2 activation and obesity.

Considering the physiological induction of differentiation of preadipocytes to adipocytes, NRF2 might be crucial as its levels are increased during the early stages of differentiation specifically affecting the expression of C/ebp β , but decrease at the later stages and in mature murine adipocytes [36–38]. Selected examples for *in vivo* studies on the role of NRF2 modulation in adipocytes are presented in Table 2. The NRF2 activation either chemically-induced by sulforaphane, or *via* Keap1 knockdown (KD) inhibits adipogenesis or decreases total TG content in mature differentiated adipocytes. The proposed mechanisms induction of the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR) target genes, cytochrome P450 1B1 (Cyp1b1) and Gsta1 and reduction in the levels of the late adipogenic factors C/ebp α , Ppar γ and fatty acid binding protein 4 (Fabp4), which was further verified in a diet-induced obesity (DIO) model in Keap1-KD mice [37]. Knockdown of NRF2 impairs adipogenesis in 3T3-L1 murine preadipocytes while suppression of Keap1 accelerates it even further, and the adipogenesis induction is marked with increase in ROS production and activation of NRF2 [37]. The Ppar β/δ agonist GW501516, similarly to the NRF2 inhibitor trigonelline, suppresses the fructose-induced NRF2 activation in adipocytes and respectively the increase in cluster of differentiation 36 (Cd36) levels, which in turn activates c-Jun N-terminal kinase (Jnk) and leads to subsequent increase in inflammatory markers. Activation of Ppar β/δ and high fructose contributes to induction of WAT inflammation through Cd36 and inhibition of NRF2 [39]. Park et al. [40] in a model of obesity-induced lipotoxicity suggest that niclosamide activates NRF2 *via* increase in p62 phosphorylation mediated by AMP-activated protein kinase (Ampk), which leads to autophagic degradation of Keap1. The NRF2-mediated induction of Gsta1, Nqo1 and Ho1 restores the redox balance disrupted from palmitic acid treatment [40]. Brassinin, which is an NRF2 activator, suppresses lipid accumulation at the late stage of preadipocytes differentiation *via* inhibition of C/ebp α and Ppar γ . Furthermore, in a co-culture model of 3T3-L1 cells and the murine

macrophages cell line RAW264.7, brassinin-induced NRF2 activation increases the levels of adiponectin, Ho1, Il-6 and Mcp-1 and alleviates obesity-induced inflammation in both adipocytes and macrophages [41]. Parthenolide activates NRF2 in both adipocytes and macrophages in an obesity co-culture model, leading to alleviation of inflammation and normalization of adiponectin and resistin levels. An additional mechanism for the anti-inflammatory effects of parthenolide is the inhibition of Nf- κ b nuclear translocation and activation, connected with activation of NRF2. The levels of Nf- κ b-regulated Il-6 and Mcp-1 were reduced only in NRF2 expressing cells, but not in NRF2-silenced ones [18]. Correspondingly, in the same model system of obesity-induced inflammation Kim et al. [42] proposed that the beneficial effect of the red ginseng-derived extract is mediated by Nf- κ b inhibition and NRF2 activation, which increased the levels of Ho1, Sod, Cat and Gpx. This conclusion is in agreement with the anti-inflammatory effects of many NRF2 activators of distinct chemical classes, which are partially NRF2-dependent [43].

The role of NRF2 in adipocyte differentiation was verified further in *in vivo* murine models and examples of recent studies are presented in Table 3. Consistent with the data from *in vitro* models, the deletion of NRF2 disrupts the adipocyte differentiation process mainly by affecting C/ebp β and Ppar γ protein levels in both wild type (WT) and leptin-deficient mice [44,45]. The complex role of the transcription factor in lipid and glucose metabolism is exerted by regulation of the expression of a number of adipogenic genes, such as Fabp4, Cebpa, Cebp β , Srebp1c, Ppar γ , fatty acid synthase (Fas) and acetyl-CoA carboxylase (Acc), altered function of the pentose phosphate pathway, and Nadph production. Deficiency of NRF2 has been reported to impair Akt activation and the glucose transporter type 4 (Glut4) function in response to insulin [46]. Interestingly however, NRF2-deficient mice are not insulin resistant [47].

The ubiquitous expression of NRF2 in various cell types suggests that its metabolic and antioxidant regulatory effects may not be tissue specific. In addition to altering adipocyte function, the activation of NRF2 prevents metabolic dysregulation and insulin resistance in lipodystrophic mice through repression of hepatic enzymes for *de novo* lipogenesis, such as fatty acid synthase (Fas) and acetyl-CoA carboxylase (Acc), and this effect was absent in NRF2-deficient animals. A direct effect on adipose tissue or on Notch signaling in adipocytes was not observed in this model [48]. Pharmacological intervention with the potent NRF2 activator CDDO-imidazole leads to downregulation of genes involved in fatty acid synthesis, decreased body weight (BW), fat tissue mass, TGs, and Fas, and increased energy expenditure, resulting

Table 2
Selected examples of the role of NRF2 in experimental *in vitro* cell models of obesity.

Experimental cell model	Modifications	Treatment (μ M)	Effect on NRF2	Key findings	Reference
MEFs	NRF2 ^{+/+} , NRF2 ^{-/-} , p62 ^{+/+} , p62 ^{-/-}	Niclosamide 5 μ M	Activation	NRF2 activation prevented palmitic acid-induced lipotoxicity	[40]
3T3-L1, RAW264.7 and co-culture	NRF2 and Ho1 knockdown	Parthenolide 1, 2, 4 μ M	Activation	Regulated adiponectin and resistin in 3T3-L1 and increased Ho1 levels in both adipocytes and macrophages	[18]
MEFs	WT and <i>ob/ob</i>	Sulforaphane 10 μ M	Activation	NRF2 chemical activation inhibits adipogenesis and decrease lipid content in differentiated adipocytes	[38]
ST-2	Transfection	-	Overexpression	NRF2 is inhibited in mature adipocytes compared to differentiating preadipocytes	[36]
SGBS and 3T3-L1	High fructose 25 mM	GW501516 (PPAR β / δ agonist) 10 μ M, GSK0660 (PPAR β / δ antagonist) 10 μ M or trigonelline 0.5 μ M	Inhibition	PPAR β / δ activation increased Akt phosphorylation and prevented fructose-induced CD36 increase <i>via</i> NRF2 inhibition	[39]
3T3-L1 and primary preadipocytes from C57BL/6J mice	NRF2-KD, Keap1-KD, NRF2-KD:Keap1-KD	Sodium arsenite 10 μ M	Activation/inhibition	NRF2 deficiency impaired adipogenesis through decrease in Ppar γ and C/eb β levels	[37]
3T3-L1, RAW264.7 and co-culture	NRF2-KD or Ho1-KD	Brassinin 50, 100 and 200 μ M	Activation/inhibition	In co-culture model of adipocytes and macrophages, brassinin increased the levels of NRF2, Ho1, and adiponectin, and decreased the levels of Il-6 and M α p-1	[41]

-, no treatment; 3T3-L1, murine adipocytes; KD, knockdown; MEFs, mouse embryonic fibroblasts; *ob/ob*, leptin deficient obese mice; SGBS, human adipocytes; ST2, bone marrow-derived stromal cells; RAW264.7, murine macrophages; WT, wild type.

in obesity prevention in high fat diet (HFD)-fed WT, but has no effect in NRF2-deficient mice [49], which was confirmed in another study [50]. Sampath et al. [51] found that NRF2 activation in WT mice on HFD prevented the increase in BW, circulating glucose, leptin, Il-6, Tnf- α , M α p-1 and oxidative stress by increase in NO generation in the gastrointestinal tract through activation of GTP cyclohydrolase 1/tetrahydrobiopterin/neuronal Nos (Gch1/Bh4/nNos) pathway. Furthermore, induction of the Erk/Jnk pathway, inhibition of AhR, increased expression of estrogen receptors, activation of p38 mitogen-activated protein kinase (p38 Mapk) have all been implicated in the NRF2-mediated anti-inflammatory systemic effects in obesity.

Consistently, beneficial effects of NRF2 activation have been observed in a diet-induced obesity model of depression represented as improved lipid profile, insulin sensitivity and restored balance of the hippocampal antioxidant enzymes Sod, Cat, Gpx and the levels of Gsh possibly mediated by upregulation of Akt/Creb [52]. In models of NASH, the pathology of which is highly comorbid with obesity, NRF2-deficient mice show accelerated disease pathogenesis [47]; conversely, the non-canonical NRF2 activation *via* p62-mediated Keap1 inhibition protects murine hepatocytes from lipotoxicity and oxidative stress [40]. Activation of NRF2 with curcumin treatment in muscle and liver tissues, but not in WAT, decreases oxidative stress and improves insulin sensitivity in HFD mice [53]. Taken together, these data suggest that in models of diet-induced obesity activation of NRF2 is predominantly beneficial as it prevents the increase in fat mass and decrease the oxidative burden. However, there are opposing results from studies with NRF2-knockout mice suggesting that deletion of the transcription factor increases the levels of fibroblast growth factor 21 (Fgf21) in HFD-fed mice compared to WT mice, as well as lowers their body weight, leptin and glucose levels [54].

Leptin has a crucial role as a signaling molecule for normal adipogenesis and regulation of the balance between fat tissue mass and satiety control in the arcuate and paraventricular regions in the hypothalamus which are rich in NO sensitive neurons [2,55]. These brain regions are highly sensitive to oxidative stress and disrupted leptin signaling in either adipose tissue or the respective leptin-sensitive neurons could interfere with changes in NRF2 activity as a key transcription factor for the cell defense against oxidants. Several studies in *ob/ob* leptin-deficient obese mice have confirmed the interaction between leptin and NRF2 [36,38,46]. Adipogenic markers and antioxidant enzymes (Ho1, Nqo1, Sod3, Gpx2, Gpx4 and thioredoxin reductase) are increased in *ob/ob* mice compared to WT animals, but the deletion of NRF2 disrupts the adaptive antioxidant response [44]. The knockdown of Keap1 resulted in greater degree of NRF2 activation in *ob/ob* mice compared to WT mice suggesting that the decreased leptin and the hyperlipidemia in obesity are inducing factors for NRF2 activation. In leptin-deficient obese mice NRF2 activation leads to decreased adipose tissue mass, suppressed Ppar γ activity and lipid accumulation in WAT, but worsens hepatic steatosis and glucose tolerance [38].

Pharmacological Keap1-dependent activation of NRF2 counteracts HFD-induced inflammation and oxidative stress. Potentially contributing mechanisms to these effects are the upregulation of Ho1 and the activation of anti-inflammatory pathways driven by p38/Jnk/Erk, Mapk and Nf- κ b [18]. The NRF2 activation is necessary for amelioration of the damaging effects of high fat and fructose diet (HFFD). Sharma et al. [5] showed that pharmacological activation of NRF2 in HFFD-consuming mice by the tricyclic cyanone inducer TBE-31 leads to suppression of inflammation, decrease in lipogenesis and prevention of hepatosteatosis. Another transcription factor participating in the adipogenic differentiation and adipose tissue expansion is Ppar β / δ . High fructose diet feeding in Ppar β / δ -KO mice leads to induction of WAT inflammation through Cd36 and activation of NRF2. In Ppar β / δ -KO mice, the levels of Tnf- α , M α p-1, and Nqo1 are increased in adipose tissue, suggesting that NRF2 regulation on adipogenesis has links with Ppar β / δ [39].

Table 3
Selected examples of the role of NRF2 in experimental *in vivo* models of obesity and its related complications.

Experimental model/groups	Diet modification	Treatment (mg/kg b.w.)	Effect on NRF2	Key findings	Reference
C57BL/6J female mice WT and NRF2 ^{-/-}	HFD	Cinnamaldehyde 50 mg/kg b.w.	Activation	NRF2 activation in WT mice on HFD normalized BW, decreased oxidative stress by increase in NO levels and normalized delayed gastric emptying	[51]
C57BL/6J mice WT, AdNICD, Keap1KD:WT, Keap1KD:AdNICD, NRF2KO:Keap1KD:WT, NRF2KO:Keap1KD:AdNICD	-	-	Activation/inhibition	NRF2 activation by knocking-down <i>Keap1</i> in a mouse model of overexpression of the Notch intracellular domain in adipocytes (AdNICD) prevented hepatic steatosis, dyslipidemia, and insulin resistance	[48]
C57BL/6J mice	HFFD	Allicin 50, 100 and 200 mg/kg b.w.	Activation	Allicin administration decreased BW after HFD, normalized serum lipids, glucose, insulin and ROS levels <i>via</i> activation of NRF2/Ho1	[52]
C57BL/6J mice	HCD	Niclosamide 50 mg/kg b.w.	Activation	NRF2 activation protected murine hepatocytes from lipotoxicity and oxidative stress	[40]
C57BL/6J mice WT and NRF2-disrupted	HFD	CDDO-imidazole 30 μmol/kg b.w.	Activation/inhibition	CDDO-imidazole activation of NRF2 downregulated lipogenic genes in liver but not adipose tissue	[49]
C57BL/6J mice	HFD	Curcumin 50 mg/kg b.w.	Activation	Curcumin activation of NRF2 improved insulin sensitivity and alleviated inflammation in obesity	[53]
C57BL/6J mice WT, NRF2 ^{-/-} , <i>ob/ob</i> , NRF2 ^{-/-} : <i>ob/ob</i> , NRF2(f ^{-/-} : <i>ob/ob</i> and NRF2(f ^{+/-} : <i>ob/ob</i>)	-	-	Deletion	NRF2 knockout in leptin-deficient <i>ob/ob</i> mice systemically or specifically in adipocytes resulted in a decrease in body weight, but exacerbated IR, hyperglycemia and hyperlipidemia	[44]
C57BL/6J mice	HFD	Parthenolide 1 and 10 mg/kg b.w.	Activation	Parthenolide decreased BW, alleviate obesity-induced inflammation by regulating M2/M1 ratio, decreased NF-κB, Mapk, Jnk, Erk and p38	[18]
C57BL/6J mice WT, NRF2 ^{-/-} , <i>ob/ob</i> , NRF2 ^{-/-} : <i>ob/ob</i> and KEAP1-KD	-	-	Deletion	NRF2 knockout in leptin-deficient mice disrupted adipocyte differentiation, decreased fat mass, but led to glucose and insulin intolerance and in WT mice led to increased adipose mass	[46]
C57BL/6J mice WT, <i>ob/ob</i> , Keap1-KD and Keap1-KD: <i>ob/ob</i>	HFD	-	Activation	Keap1-KD resulted in greater degree of NRF2 activation in <i>ob/ob</i> mice suggesting the hyperlipidemia in obesity as inducing factor for NRF2 activity. NRF2 activation in leptin-deficient obese mice decreased adipose tissue mass, Pparγ expression and lipid accumulation in WAT, but worsened hepatic steatosis and glucose tolerance	[38]
C57BL/6J mice WT and NRF2-KO	HFD	-	Deletion	The metabolic effects of NRF2 activation in HFD-induced obesity were mediated at least partially by Fgf21	[54]
C57BL/6J WT and NRF2-KO mice	HFFD	TBE-31	Activation	TBE-31 activated NRF2 in HFFD-fed mice, leading to suppressed inflammation, decreased lipogenesis and prevented diet-induced hepatosteatosis	[5]
C57BL/6 × 129/SV WT and Pparβ/δ-KO mice	HFFD	-	Activation	<i>Pparβ/δ</i> -KO mice had increased Tnf-α, Mcp-1 in adipose tissue and increased levels of NRF2 and Ngq1	[39]

-, no diet modification or no treatment; AdNICD, murine model of partial lipodystrophy induced by adipocyte-specific upregulation of Notch intracellular domain (NICD); b.w., body weight; HFD, high fat diet; HCD, high carbohydrate diet; HFFD, high fat and fructose diet; KD, knockdown; KO, knockout; NRF2^{-/-}, knockout for NRF2; *ob/ob*, leptin deficient phenotype; TBE-31, tricyclic bis(cyanone) compound.

Fig. 2. Schematic presentation of the interconnections between NRF2 activation and transcription factors participating in the regulation of adipogenesis and obesity-induced inflammation (modified from Hayes and Dinkova-Kostova [23]).

The selected experimental data were analyzed with the aim to reveal the potential of NRF2 modulation in obesity management. Previously defined interactions between NRF2 and transcription factors regulating metabolic processes in connection with obesity were confirmed and new potential players were suggested, such as the PPAR β/δ negative regulation on NRF2. A schematic presentation of these interconnections was modified from the comprehensive work of Hayes and Dinkova-Kostova [23] and is depicted in Fig. 2.

The overall data from adipocytes *in vitro* is pointing towards the conclusion that the pharmacological activation of NRF2 in obesity is beneficial and alleviates obesity-induced inflammation in both fat cells and in co-cultured macrophages. When using DIO wild-type animal models the induction of NRF2-mediated response is positive, leading to prevention of obesity-induced inflammation, hepatosteatosis, IR and excessive lipogenesis. However, when leptin deficiency is present, the NRF2 activation is detrimental to the metabolic balance and, despite the weight loss, is worsening glucose tolerance and hepatic functions.

5. Conclusions

Considering the complexity of the NRF2 mediated effects and their context dependency, it is inappropriate to define that NRF2 activation as strictly beneficial or harmful. Moreover, when the pathology that is targeted is so complex NCD as obesity, it would be naive to search for a unidirectional link. Obesity is a health problem that usually develops over many years and involves the interplay of multiple factors, including physiological, genetic, nutritional and psychological. Fine-tuning of a complex process such as energy and redox balance could be hypothetically achieved by the modulation of a master regulator of cytoprotection such as the transcription factor NRF2. However, more detailed research is needed to clarify the potential implementation of NRF2 modulation in obesity.

6. Future research needs

Controversial data is reported on NRF2 activation regarding the presence or absence of leptin- and/or insulin-resistance in obesity. Further research aiming to target in more depth the link between KEAP1/NRF2 pathway and leptin signaling is much needed. Moreover, confirmation of the reported beneficial effects from NRF2 activation in human adipocytes is lacking and would be of potential interest to be explored. Co-cultures of human macrophages and adipocytes or of hippocampal neurons and adipocytes represent also a great possibility to clarify the role of NRF2 activity in the complex context of obesity.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing interest.

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